

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Isolation and characterisation of coronary endothelial cells from patients with acute myocardial infarction.

Short title: Gallogly - Coronary endothelial cells from thrombectomy

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Contents: Detailed methodology and on-line tables and figures

DETAILED METHODS

Study population

Atherothrombotic specimens from patients receiving emergency percutaneous coronary intervention and manual thrombus aspiration for acute ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (n=49) were collected into complete EGM™-2 BulletKit™ medium ('EGM™-2'; Cat no. CC-3162; Lonza, UK) supplemented with 10% HyClone™ fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Cat no. 12379802; Fisher Scientific, UK). Venous blood from patients with prior myocardial infarction (100ml) was drawn from the median cubital vein and placed in 8ml of 3.8% sodium citrate (n=3). All samples were processed within 24 hours and subjects provided written informed consent. Ethical approval was obtained from the Lothian Research Ethics Committee (Edinburgh; UK) and this study was conducted in accordance with the declaration of Helsinki and institutional guidelines.

Cell isolation

Endothelial cells were grown on tissue culture plastics pre-coated with type I rat-tail collagen (Cat no. 356400; BD Bioscience, UK) and maintained in EGM™-2 medium supplemented with 10% HyClone™ FBS unless otherwise stated.

Coronary endothelial outgrowth (CEO) cells were isolated from atherothrombotic specimens (n=37). Specimens were washed with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) and manually disaggregated using sterile surgical scalpels. Tissue explants were seeded into 1 well of a 6-well tissue culture plate and maintained under standard cell culture conditions. After 24 hours, tissue explants, non-adherent cells, and debris were aspirated. Medium was changed every other day until first passage. Cells were left in culture 15-28 days (dependent on proliferative activity) prior to first passage.

Late endothelial outgrowth cells (EOCs) were isolated from the mononuclear cell fraction of whole blood (100ml) by buoyant density centrifugation over Ficoll-Paque PLUS (Cat no. 17-1440-03; GE Healthcare, Sweden) (n=3). Without further cell subpopulation enrichment procedures, 10×10^6 MNCs were resuspended in 2 wells of a 6-well tissue culture plate. After 24 hours, non-adherent cells were aspirated and fresh media was added^{1,2}. EOCs were characterized by their 'cobblestone' morphology and cells were maintained for 21 days in culture prior to first passage.

Human coronary artery endothelial cells (HCAECs) (Cat. CC-2585; Lonza, UK), pooled human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) (CC-2519; Lonza, UK and Cat. C-12203 Promocell, Germany) and single donor HUVECs (Cat. C-003-5C; Invitrogen, UK) were acquired commercially.

Cells were treated in an identical manner and experimental numbers are biological repeats for all except HCAECs, which are results from 3 independent experiments.

Cellular characterisation of atherothrombotic specimens

Immunohistochemistry

Freshly isolated whole atherothrombotic specimens were formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded (n=8). Specimens were cut longitudinally into 5µm segments, deparaffinized with xylene and rehydrated with increasing concentrations of alcohol.

For Hematoxylin and Eosin staining, specimens were stained with hematoxylin for 5 minutes, rinsed with distilled water for 15 minutes and then stained with eosin for 1 minute. For the Carstairs' method for fibrin and platelet staining, specimens were stained with 5% Ferric Ammonium Sulphate for 5 minutes, Mayer's hematoxylin for 5 minutes and Picric Acid-orange G solution for 45 minutes. Slides were then washed and stained with Ponceau Fuchsin solution for 1 minute, 1% phosphotungstic acid for 2 minutes and Anilin blue solution for 10 minutes as previously described³. Slides were then washed in tap water and air dried overnight before coverslips were applied. All histological reagents were provided by Electron Microscopy Services (USA). For CD146 staining, epitopes were retrieved by boiling specimens in 1mM ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) solution for 20 minutes prior to endogenous peroxidase activity quenching by 3% hydrogen peroxide. Specimens were treated with Endogenous Avidin/Biotin Blocking Kit (Cat no. Ab3387; Abcam, UK) according to the manufacturers' instructions and non-specific antibody binding was prevented by incubating specimens with 10% normal horse serum (Cat no. S-200; Vector Laboratories, Inc., USA) in PBS. Specimens were incubated with monoclonal anti-human CD146 (Cat. Ab49492; Abcam, UK) in PBS with 2% normal horse serum overnight at 4°C, washed in PBS, and incubated with biotinylated horse anti-mouse secondary antibody (Cat no. BA-200; Vector Laboratories, Inc., USA) for 30 minutes at room temperature. The Vectastain Elite ABC Peroxidase kit (Cat no. PK-4000; Vector Laboratories, Inc., USA) was used for secondary antibody detection and visualization occurred using 3,3'-Diaminobenzidine (DAB) as the substrate (Cat no. SK-4100; Vector Laboratories, Inc., USA).

Flow cytometry

Freshly isolated whole atherothrombotic specimens were washed with PBS and manually disaggregated (n=4). A single cell homogenate was achieved following enzymatic disaggregation in PBS containing 1mg/1ml type I collagenase (Cat. 17018-029; Life Technologies, UK) in a 37°C shaking water bath at 180rpm for 60 minutes, followed by passing cells through a 100µm sterile nylon mesh. Cells were recovered by centrifugation and resuspended in EGMTM-2 medium. 100µl cell suspension was

incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature with monoclonal antibodies conjugated to specific fluorochromes: LIVE/DEAD® Fixable Dead Cell Stains-V525, CD42a-FITC, CD45-V450, CD146-PE/Cy7 and CD31-PE (**Online Table III**). After washing, cells were fixed and erythrocytes lysed simultaneously using BD FACST™ Lysing Solution (Cat no. 349202; BD Biosciences, UK). Samples were washed and then analyzed using a BD LSRFortessa™ II cell analyzer. Unstained samples were used as controls. Spectral overlap and compensation was calculated and verified manually for each antibody using anti-mouse BD™ CompBead (Cat no. 552843, BD Biosciences, UK). A minimum of 200,000 events was collected for data analysis using FlowJo version 10.0.6 (TreeStar Inc., Switzerland). Endothelial cells were identified by the placement of population gates based on the unstained control. Following scatter selection and doublet discrimination, viable cells were selected by exclusion of LIVE/DEAD® Fixable Dead Cell Stain-V525. CD42a and CD45 positive cells were excluded to avoid platelets, hematopoietic cells and leucocytes and endothelial cells were identified by their expression of CD146 or CD31 (**Online Figure II**).

Phenotypic characterisation of endothelial cells

Immunocytochemistry

Endothelial cells (Passage 1-4) grown on tissue culture vessels pre-coated with type I rat-tail collagen were washed twice with PBS and fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (Cat. PF101; FD Neuro technologies Inc., USA) for 10 minutes at room temperature. Cells were permeabilized with 0.1% Triton™ X-100 (Cat. T9284; Sigma Aldrich, UK) for 5 minutes, and then incubated with 2% normal goat serum (NGS) (Cat no. S-1000; Vector Laboratories Inc., USA) in PBS for 30 minutes to block non-specific staining. Cells were incubated overnight at 4°C with monoclonal antibodies: rabbit anti-human CD31, mouse anti-human von Willebrand Factor (vWF) antibodies (**Online Table I**) and isotype controls for mouse primary antibody (Cat no. 086599; Invitrogen, UK) and rabbit primary antibody (Cat no. 086199; Invitrogen, UK). Cells were washed and incubated with fluorescent-labelled secondary antibodies for 30 minutes: Alexa Fluor® 488 goat anti-rabbit or Alexa Fluor® 647 goat anti-mouse to detect CD31 and vWF, respectively (**Online Table I**). Cells were washed in PBS, rinsed in tap water and mounted using ProLong® Gold Antifade Reagent with 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) (Cat no. P36935; Invitrogen, UK). Cover slips were applied and slides were dried at room temperature in the dark for 1 hour prior to analysis.

Flow cytometry

Endothelial cells (Passage 1-4) were trypsinized from tissue culture vessels and aliquots of 1×10^5 cells were resuspended in 100 μ l EGMTM-2 medium and incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature with pre-conjugated monoclonal antibodies: CD146-PECy7, CD31-FITC, CD105-APC, CD144-PE, CD54-PE, CD34-APC/Cy7, CD309-PE, CD133-APC, CD117-PE, CD106-FITC and CD45-V450 (**Online Table III**). For cytoplasmic antigens, 1×10^5 cells were permeabilized using BD Cytotfix/CytopermTM Fixation/Permeabilization solution (Cat no. 554714; BD Biosciences, UK) prior to incubation with monoclonal pre-conjugated antibodies: vWF-FITC and eNOS-PE (**Online Table III**). After washing, cells were fixed using BD FACSTTM Lysing Solution (Cat no. 349202; BD Biosciences, UK). Cells were washed and analyzed using a BD LSRFortessaTM II cell analyzer. Unstained cells were used as controls. Spectral overlap and compensation was calculated and verified manually for each antibody using anti-mouse BDTM CompBead (Cat no. 552843, BD Biosciences, UK). A minimum of 5,000 events in the relevant gate was collected for data analysis using FlowJo version 10.0.6 (TreeStar Inc., Switzerland)

Uptake of Dil-acetylated low density lipoprotein

Confluent monolayers of CEO cells were incubated with 1,1'-dioctadecyl-3,3,3'-tetramethylindocarbocyanine-labelled acetylated low density lipoprotein (LDL) (Cat no. L-3484; Life Technologies, UK) (1 μ g/ml) for 4 hours at 37°C (n=3). Samples were then washed and visualized with a fluorescent Zeiss Axio Observer microscope (Zeiss, Germany).

Functional characterisation of endothelial cells

Growth kinetics

At second and subsequent passages, seeding density (C_s), days in culture (t) and harvested cell number (C_h) were recorded. Population doubling time (PDT) was calculated according to the equation: $PDT = \frac{\log^2(C_h/C_s)}{t}$ as previously described¹. Cumulative population doubling levels (CPDL) (the sum of all population doublings) were also calculated.

Adhesion assay

Endothelial cells were trypsinized from tissue culture plastics and aliquots of 4×10^4 cells were resuspended in 1ml EGMTM-2 medium and seeded into 1 well of a BD BioCoat Collagen I coated 6 well plate for 30 minutes. Wells were gently washed to remove non-adherent cells and mosaics of digital photographs across the centre of the well were captured. Attachment within a defined region of each well was quantified and expressed as a percentage of seeded cell number⁴.

Wound migration assay

Endothelial cells were grown to 90% confluence and rendered quiescent by incubation with serum-free EGM™-2 medium for 24 hours at 37°C. A linear vertical ‘wound’ was created across the diameter of the 6 well plate using a sterile P1000 pipette tip. Cells were then washed and replenished with serum-free EGM™-2 medium. Sets of digital images were taken at 0 hours and 24 hours. To quantify migration, the width of the wound was visualized at the start time (0 hours) and the area of wound closure across the vertical stroke at 24 hours was quantified and expressed as a percentage of wound closure⁴.

Angiogenesis assay

BD Matrigel™ basement membrane matrix (Cat no. 365231; BD Pharmingen, UK) was thawed on ice and 150µl was laid into a Corning® Costar® 48 well, flat bottom cell culture plates (Cat. CLS3548; Sigma Aldrich, UK) and incubated for 30 minutes at 37°C. After gelification, 2×10^4 cells in 100µl EGM™-2 medium supplemented with 10% HyClone™ FBS were seeded onto the Matrigel™. After 24 hours, mosaics of digital images across the entire well were captured. Tubule formation was quantified as the number of complete tubule structures present in the 48 well plate.

Subcutaneous sponge implantation assay for *in vivo* angiogenesis

Male NOD-SCID gamma mice (NOD.Cg-PrkdcscidIl2rgtm1Wjl/SzJ) (Stock no. 005557; Charles River, UK) aged 10-12 weeks (CEO cells and EOCs n=12 each, 3 biological repeats; HUVECs n=4, 1 biological repeat) were purchased and maintained in the Biomedical research facility at Edinburgh University. All animal experiments were carried out in accordance with the British Home Office Animals (Scientific Procedures) Act 1986 in accordance with institutional guidelines.

Endothelial cells were trypsinized from tissue culture vessels and aliquots of 1×10^5 cells were resuspended in 100µl 1:1 EGM™-2/phenol free GFR Matrigel™ (Cat 356231; BD Biosciences, UK). Sterilised sponge cylinders (0.5cm/1cm) (Caligen Foam, U.K) were compressed into this suspension and incubated for 30 minutes at 37°C. EGM™-2/phenol free GFR Matrigel™ sponges were prepared as matched controls. Mice were anaesthetized intraperitoneally with Domitor containing Medetomidine and Vetalar containing Ketamine; both were administered at 0.1ml per 10g body weight. Upon sedation, an analgesic, Vetergesic containing buprenorphine was administered subcutaneously at 0.1mg per kg body weight. Matrigel™ sponges (vehicle control) were implanted subcutaneously into the left flank and cell-embedded sponges were implanted in the right flank⁵. The sides of the wound were apposed with a forceps and closed using skin staples (9mm Autoclips; Cat no. NC9050532; Fisher Scientific, USA). After surgery, a reversal agent, Antisedan-containing Atipamezole, was administered subcutaneously at 0.05ml per 10g body weight and the mice observed on a heat mat until recovery. The wound was observed daily throughout the experiment and after 7 days the staples were removed. After

21 days, mice were sacrificed by cervical dislocation and the sponges removed. Sponges were fixed in 4% PFA overnight, then transferred to 70% ethanol and stored at 4°C.

Chalkley count

Fixed sponges were paraffin-embedded and cut transversely into 4µm section. Sections were deparaffinized, rehydrated and stained with hematoxylin and eosin as before. Vessel density within sponges was quantified using the Chalkley count^{2, 5, 6}. The three most vascular areas (hot spots) with the highest number of microvessel profiles were chosen subjectively from each slide (3 slides per sponge per animal). Using a x20 objective, a 25-point Chalkley eyepiece graticule (NG52 Chalkley Point Array 26mm; Cat no. 01B26257; Pyser-SGI Ltd, UK) was applied to each hot-spot area and oriented to permit the maximum number of dot-perfusing vessel intersections (which were defined by the presence of red blood cells). The Chalkley score was determined by the sum of points coinciding with a vessel.

Immunohistochemistry

The presence of human cells within murine vessels was determined using human specific monoclonal antibodies to endothelial antigens⁵. Paraffin embedded 4µm sections of sponges were deparaffinized and rehydrated prior to antigen retrieval with Tris based buffer at 100°C for 20 minutes. Specimens were cooled for 40 minutes at room temperature, then washed in PBS, permeabilized and incubated with 10% NGS as before. Specimens were incubated overnight at 4°C with monoclonal antibodies: human specific mouse anti-CD146 and cross-reactive rabbit anti-CD31 (*Online Table I*). Specimens were washed and incubated with fluorescent-labelled secondary antibodies: Alexa Fluor® 488 goat anti-mouse and Alexa Fluor® 568 goat anti-rabbit to detect CD146 and CD31, respectively (*Online Table I*). Slides were then rinsed in tap water and mounted as before. The EGM™-2/ phenol free GFR Matrigel™ -only sponges were used as negative control for human cells. Human fibroid tissue was used as a positive human control for primary antibody immunoreactivity. Using a x20 objective, three hotspot regions were chosen subjectively from each slide based on visual scanning for cross-reactive CD31 positive vessels (red). Composite multicolor images of each region were generated, CD31-positive and human-specific CD146-positive vessels (green) were counted, and the percentage of CD146-positive vessels was calculated.

Image analysis

Carstairs histological images were captured using the Olympus Provis AX-70 microscope (Olympus, USA). All other images were captured using a fluorescent Zeiss Axio Observer microscope (Zeiss, Germany). All images were processed using AxioVision 4.8 software (Carl Zeiss, Germany) and Photoshop version CS5 (Adobe, USA) was used when image quantification was required.

Statistical analysis

Data are shown as mean \pm standard deviation. Independent samples were analyzed using the unpaired Student's *t*-test. More than two groups were compared using repeated measure or one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Bonferroni post-tests where appropriate. Categorical data were compared using the chi-squared with Fisher's exact test. Paired Student's *t*-tests were used to compare Chalkley counts between vehicle control- and cell-infiltrated sponges. Statistical significance was assumed if a null hypothesis could be rejected at $P \leq 0.05$.

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Online Figures Legends

Online Figure I: Atherothrombotic specimen allocation.

Atherothrombotic specimens were fixed for histological (n=8) and flow cytometric (n=4) examination and were physically disaggregated for cell culture (n=37). 27/37 (73%) of atherothrombotic specimens gave rise to coronary endothelial outgrowth.

Online Figure II: Representative figure for flow cytometric analysis of atherothrombotic specimens.

Gating strategy for the identification of viable $CD42a^+CD45^+CD146^+$ and $CD42a^+CD45^+CD31^+$ cells within atherothrombotic specimens. Following doublet discrimination (**A**) and scatter selection (**B**), viable cells were selected by exclusion of LIVE/DEAD® Fixable Dead Cell Stain-V525 (**C**). $CD42a^+$ (**D**) and $CD45^+$ (**E**) positive cells were selected to avoid contamination by platelets, hematopoietic cells and leucocytes. Endothelial cells were identified by expression $CD146^+$ (**F**) or $CD31^+$ (**G**).

Online Tables

Online Table I: Suppliers of primary and secondary antibodies for immunocytochemistry.

Antibody	Raised in	Reactivity	Supplier	Catalogue no.	Concentration
Primary					
CD31	Rabbit	Mouse/Human	Abcam	ab28364	1:100
vWF	Mouse	Human	BD Pharmingen	555849	1:250
CD146	Mouse	Human	Abcam	ab49492	1:50
Secondary					
Biotinylated anti-mouse IgG	Horse	Mouse	Vector Laboratories	BA-2000	1:250
AF488	Goat	Rabbit	Life Technologies	A11034	1:200
AF647	Goat	Mouse	Life Technologies	A21240	1:200
AF488	Goat	Mouse	Life Technologies	A11001	1:200
AF568	Goat	Rabbit	Life Technologies	A11011	1:200

vWF= von Willebrand factor.

Online Table II: Antigens routinely used to identify endothelial cells.

Antigen	Alternative name	Endothelial cell function
Cell surface		
CD146	MCAM	Cell adhesion molecule located at endothelial cell junctions. Facilitates endothelial cell-cell interactions ⁷ .
CD31	PECAM-1	Cell adhesion molecule. A dynamic regulator of endothelial cell behavior by modulation of tyrosine phosphorylated b-catenin ⁸ .
CD105	Endoglin	Accessory receptor for transforming growth factor-beta receptor. Important for endothelial migration and survival during inflammation ⁹ .
CD54	ICAM-1	Cell adhesion molecule. Facilitates transmigration of leucocytes through the endothelium ¹⁰ .
CD144	VE-Cadherin	Cell adhesion molecule (cadherin). Regulates endothelium permeability ¹¹ .
CD34	HPCA-1	Cell adhesion molecule. Modulates leucocyte cellular adhesion at portal entry sites on the endothelium ¹² .
CD309	KDR	Receptor for vascular endothelial growth factor. Modules angiogenesis ¹³ .
CD133	Prominin-1	Pentaspanspan trans-membrane glycoprotein. Function in the endothelium is unknown ¹⁴ .
CD117	c-Kit	Receptor for stem cell factor. Function in the endothelium is unknown.
CD106	VCAM-1	Cell adhesion molecule. Facilitates leucocyte attachment to the endothelium (expression only upon cytokine stimulation) ¹⁰ .
Cytoplasmic		
vWF	-	Protein. Important in hemostasis and the regulation of thrombogenesis and fibrinolysis.
eNOS	-	Enzyme. Generation of nitric oxide and the regulation of vasodilation and vasoconstriction.

eNOS= endothelial nitric oxide synthase; HPCA= hematopoietic progenitor cell antigen; ICAM= intracellular adhesion molecule; KDR= kinase domain receptor; MCAM= melanoma cell adhesion molecule; PECAM= platelet endothelial cell adhesion molecule; VCAM= vascular cell adhesion molecule; VE= vascular endothelial; vWF= von Willebrand factor.

Online Table III: Suppliers of antibodies for flow cytometry.

Antibody	Fluorochrome	Supplier	Catalogue no.	Concentration
Cell phenotyping				
Panel I				
CD31	FITC	BD Biosciences	555445	1:100
CD146	Pe/Cy7	Biolegend	342010	1:100
CD34	APC/Cy7	Biolegend	343514	1:100
CD309	PE	R and D systems	P35968	1:50
CD45	V450	BD Horizon	560368	1:100
CD133	APC	Miltenyl Biotec	130-090-826	1:50
Panel II				
CD54	PE	BD Pharmingen	555511	1:100
CD106	FITC	BD Biosciences	551146	1:100
Panel III				
CD105	APC	R and D systems	FAB10971A	1:100
CD144	PE	R and D systems	FAB9381P	1:100
Panel IV				
CD117	PE	R and D systems	FAB322F	1:50
Panel V				
vWF	FITC	BD Biosciences	5601013	1:200
eNOS	PE	BD Biosciences	560103	1:100
Atherothrombotic cell analysis				
LIVE/DEAD® Fixable Dead Cell Stain	Aqua	Life Technologies	L34957	1:100
CD45	V450	BD Horizon	560368	1:100
CD31	PE	Biolegend	303106	1:50
CD146	Pe/Cy7	Biolegend	342010	1:100
CD42a	FITC	BD Pharmingen	558818	1:100

APC= Allophycocyanin; eNOS= endothelial nitric oxide synthase; FITC= fluorescein isothiocyanate; PE= Phycoerythrin; vWF= von Willebrand factor.

Online Table IV: Clinical and procedural characteristics of all patients undergoing thrombectomy for ST-segment myocardial infarction

	Total population (n=49)
Age, years	62 ± 12
Gender, male	37 (76%)
Medical history and risk factors	
Previous myocardial infarction	5 (10%)
Previous PCI/CABG	6 (12%)
Current smoker	21 (43%)
Ex-smoker	4 (8%)
Hypertension	10 (20%)
Hyperlipidemia	13 (27%)
Family history of premature coronary heart disease	17 (35%)
Diabetes mellitus	6 (12%)
Medication on admission	
Aspirin	7 (14%)
Clopidogrel	3 (6%)
B-blockers	4 (8%)
ACE-inhibitors	8 (16%)
Statins	10 (20%)
Acute coronary syndrome	
Troponin I concentration, micrograms/L	32.3 ± 18.8
Culprit vessel	
Left anterior descending artery	15 (31%)
Circumflex artery	3 (6%)
Right coronary artery	31 (63%)

Values are number (%) or mean ± standard deviation. ACE = angiotensin converting enzyme; CABG = coronary artery bypass grafting; PCI = percutaneous coronary intervention.